

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INTERNSHIP PROGRAM FOR STUDENT WITH SPECIAL NEEDS AT THE HIGH SCHOOL LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to reveal how school readiness is in the process of adding insight to the world of work and adding skills or Internships for children with special needs at the high school level. This research uses a descriptive approach. The subjects of this study were principals and teachers from several special schools. Data collection was carried out through surveys. The results of this study are as follows: schools do not yet have vocational teachers who are linear with the areas they can provide, facilities for teaching vocational education to children with special needs at the secondary level are inadequate, lack of parental involvement to be involved in the preparation of vocational programs for students with special needs, several schools have not carried out an internship program for children with special needs at the senior high school level and there has not been any cooperation with the business world and the industrial world due to the difficulty of the business world and the industrial world in accepting children with special needs for the internship program. The conclusion from the research is that to carry out an internship program, the need for collaboration between several parties, such as schools, parents, the business world, and the industrial world as well as local policymakers so that students with special needs at the high school level can also feel how to learn in work situations and are ready to continue life after graduating from school, able to be independent, and confident in working with the community.

Keywords: Internship, students with special needs, business world industry

1. Introduction

The times and the rapid globalization have not only given rise to various social, economic, cultural, and technological phenomena but also increasingly tighter levels of competition, both between countries and between individuals. Likewise, with children with special needs, they must have adequate abilities for their provision in the life to come so that children with special needs can live independently. Education for children with special needs has different principles from education for regular children (non-special needs). Children with special needs or children with special needs not only learn about the development of academic abilities but also develop their functions as a result of the obstacles they have. One of the abilities that must be possessed by children with special needs is vocational skills. This is by the special education curriculum for the upper secondary level providing an allocation of 40% for academics and 60% for vocational skills so that children with special needs at the upper secondary level are more equipped with vocational skills so that they can live independently after

graduating from school. Children with special needs also need activities or programs that support them to be able to engage and work with the community. So that special schools require a program, namely apprenticeship. According to Law Number 13 of 2003 concerning Manpower, apprenticeship is part of the job training system which is organized in an integrated manner between job training in training institutions by working directly under the guidance and supervision of instructors or workers/laborers who are more experienced, in the process of producing goods and/or services in the company, to master certain skills or expertise.¹

Vocational skills are developed as reinforcement for independent living, independent from other people and preparation for work, which includes (1) information technology and computers; (2) acupuncture; (3) electronics; (4) automotive; (5) tourism; (6) beautification; (7) culinary; (8) fashion; (9) communication; (10) journalism; (11) performing arts; and (12) fine arts and crafts². Vocational education is oriented to enter the business world and the industrial world so that graduates from special education are equivalent to other general education. The success of vocational education requires innovative strategic planning of the roles of educators and education personnel as well as government support through policies that become the umbrella of legality, thus the existence of children with special needs in the business world and the industrial world is the obligation of (1) Government, Regional Government, Business Entity State-Owned and Regional-Owned Enterprises employ at least 2% (two percent) of persons with disabilities of the total number of employees or workers.³(2) Private companies are required to employ at least 1% (one percent) of Persons with Disabilities of the total number of employees or workers. Apprenticeship is an effort to provide experience, knowledge, and real work skills about the production process in the Business and Industrial world that are needed by children with special needs at the high school level. The importance of industrial experience for children with special needs has received very serious attention by the government through the Directorate of Primary and Secondary Education. Realizing the lack of provision of industrial experience for children with special needs, the government through the Director-General of Primary and Secondary Education, should the education unit carry out an apprenticeship program in class XI for at least one month.⁴

Based on the above policy, schools are trying to carry out apprenticeships for children with special needs at the high school level, several schools have succeeded in collaborating with the Business World and the Industrial World and implementing apprenticeship programs and have even collaborated in the form of accepting graduates of children with special needs to work in their companies. . However, some schools have not collaborated with the Business World and the Industrial World and have implemented an apprenticeship program due to the lack of involvement of various parties to support the success of the apprenticeship program in special schools. The failure to implement the apprenticeship program has an impact on children with special needs at the upper secondary level who cannot explore their abilities in the industrial sector with work situations. The objective of the industrial apprenticeship program for children with special needs is to improve the quality of graduates, namely to provide them with real work experience in the Business and Industrial Worlds. Armed with

¹ Undang-undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 13 Tahun 2003 Tentang Ketenagakerjaan

² Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 157 Tahun 2014 Tentang Kurikulum Pendidikan Khusus

³ Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 8 Tahun 2016 Tentang Penyandang Disabilitas

⁴ Peraturan Direktur Jendral Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah Nomor: 10/D/KR/2017 Tentang Struktur Kurikulum, Kompetensi Inti, Kompetensi Dasar dan Pedoman Implementasi Kurikulum 2013 Pendidikan Khusus.

vocational education, children with special needs can develop themselves or work for other parties by obtaining recognition of decent income. Of course, this skills learning model requires a management system that involves various parties functionally (parents of students, schools, industry or business units, and government and society).

1.1 Vocational Learning for Children with Special Needs

By the Regulation of the Minister of Women Empowerment and Child Protection of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2011 concerning the Policy for Handling Children with Special Needs in article 3 paragraph (1), that "Policies for handling children with special needs include programs in the general fields, education, work skills training". A child has the right to education and skills training according to his abilities and talents. This requires a professional team to carry out education and training needs assessment services and implementers. This is done to obtain data about the needs and abilities of children with special needs so that the skills learning program can be appropriate and appropriate. Life skills education is provided in a self-reliance program that is oriented to prepare children with special needs to enter the world of business or the world of work (Prihatin, Diana, and Permana, 2017: 308).⁵ Thus, through vocational or skills learning, children with special needs can adapt to the community environment, live independently according to their abilities. Meanwhile, vocational skills are skills that are associated with certain fields of work and are found in society (Rapetto & Andrews, 2012: 162).⁶ Based on the structure of the special education curriculum, children with special needs at the Upper Middle School level get learning skills that are given according to the abilities and interests of the children. Learning these skills will later lead to an increase in children's vocational abilities. According to Ishartiwi (2010: 23)⁷, education for children with special needs both in regular schools and in special schools is primarily oriented towards developing the potential possessed by implementing skills learning to provide provision for useful post-school work skills for children with special needs. Unfortunately, the implementation of vocational skills learning is given at the level of learning vocational abilities (Ishartiwi, 2010: 24), so that the level of skill material provided in schools has not met the level of proficiency needed in the workforce. To support the fulfillment of this level of proficiency, an apprenticeship program is carried out.

The importance of providing vocational learning to children with special needs at the Senior High level greatly affects the level of self-adjustment ability during adulthood in society. (Heward, Alber-Morgan, & Konrad., 2017: 489) for this reason, the development of self-reliance must be managed during the transition from school to society. Career opportunities for children with special needs have limited opportunities due to the various limitations they have. Individuals with disabilities and even SLB graduates are still a minority to be employed compared to children without special needs or disabilities (Heward, Alber-Morgan, & Konrad., 2017: 499).

⁵ Prihatin, Eka, Imas Diana A. & Johar Permana. (2017). *Model Manajemen Pendidikan Life Skill pada Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*. Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan No X Hlm. 306-317.

⁶ Reppetto, Jeanne B. & W. Drew Andrews. (2012). *Handbook of Adolescent Transition Education for Youth with Disabilities: Carrer Development and Vocational Instruction*. Michael L. Wehmeyer & Kristune W. Webb Ed. New York: Routledge.

⁷ Ishartiwi. (2010). *Pembelajaran Keterampilan untuk Pemberdayaan Kemandirian Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*. Dinamika Pendidikan Majalah Ilmu Pendidikan FIP UNY nomor 02.

1.2 School Challenges in Implementing the Apprenticeship Program

The apprenticeship program is part of job training for students at companies that are partner schools. Based on Law Number 19 of 2011 concerning the ratification of the Convention On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities which regulates the fulfillment of the rights of persons with disabilities in Indonesia, it is clear that the Indonesian Government must be serious and committed to respecting, protecting and fulfilling the rights of persons with disabilities to achieve prosperity. persons with disabilities and are entitled to receive respect for their mental and physical integrity based on equality with others, including the right to receive protection and social services in the context of independence, as well as in emergencies. It is a dilemma in the implementation of this post-school transition service. Children with special needs are a vulnerable group that must be taken care of, but the need for continuity of vocational learning is also necessary.

An apprenticeship is a form of education and training that will shape the competence of students. Apprenticeship for children with special needs at the upper secondary level in its implementation is to provide direct experience to children with special needs to be involved in the world of work so that children with special needs can get structured training from someone who is an expert in their field of work. But what is a challenge for special schools to carry out apprenticeship programs for students with special needs are (1) Many special school teachers who do not match their educational background with the vocational field being taught and teachers do not have skills that can lead children with special needs to enter the world. (2) Lack of facilities and skills infrastructure that support children with special needs to master life skills at school (3) Preparation of very expensive costs to make an independent work training or workshop for children with special needs and (4) Collaboration of parties schools and the world of work that have not been well established to provide collective skills for children with special needs. Several schools in Aceh also have problems like the one above, so that schools independently conduct training for teachers who do not have vocational skills so that teachers can provide vocational learning properly according to the needs of children with special needs. Some schools also set up independent businesses in schools such as catering services, motorbike washing services, and home and office cleaning services. Thus the school has an independent business where children with special needs can learn to work and directly work with the assistance of teachers in the school. This is done so that later children with special needs can be more confident in working with the community.

2. Method

The method used in this research is descriptive. Data were collected by conducting a survey to special schools in Aceh regarding the implementation of apprenticeship programs in schools. This research uses descriptive research. The subjects of this study were school principals and teachers from several special schools.

3. Result

The challenge for special schools to implement an apprenticeship program for children with special needs is still homework the school, how can schools get out of the problem

of apprenticeship for students with special needs, such as cooperation with the business world and the industrial world, teachers who do not have skills, and adequate infrastructure. inadequate. some of these problems have shed some light on several special schools. This must be done and developed by the school considering the purpose of special education so that children with special needs can live independently and be confident to work together with the community.

4. Conclusion

The implementation of the apprenticeship program helps children with special needs to be directly involved in working in the world of work. The efforts made by the school to carry out an apprenticeship program can be carried out regularly so that in the future the program can run well and in a structured manner. There needs to be a school effort to fight for the rights of children with special needs to the officeholders in their respective regions. Further research is needed regarding the implementation of apprenticeship programs for children with special needs by individual programs that have been designed by the previous teacher or changes to the design of new individual programs.

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